

A rule-based robot grasp planner inspired by human behaviours

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Abstract—Robots are increasingly taking place in many everyday environments and industrial settings to carry out complex tasks that require high dexterity. However, obtaining high dexterity by robots is a challenge, especially when the object to manipulate is flexible and deformable. On the other hand humans grasp and manipulate effortlessly thanks to their experience gained over the years. Here we developed a rule-based robot grasp planner designed based on studies on the human grasping behaviour. In particular, the grasp planner returns the appropriate grasp strategy in terms of grasp type, grasp location, and grasp dimension, according to the symbolic representation of the current scenario.

Keywords—*Robot grasping, Grasp planning, Human behaviour, Human-Robot interaction*

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots are increasingly taking place in domestic and industrial settings where they are asked to carry out complex tasks that require proficient grasping and manipulation. However, although robotics has made vast progress in mechanical design, perception, and robust control, the robotic manipulation capabilities are limited and far from reproducing those of humans, especially when the object to grasp and manipulate is flexible and deformable [1]. Robots are skilled at grasping and manipulating known objects in repetitive and structured settings, such as industrial assembly setups. Whereas robots, humans reach, grasp, and manipulate objects naturally and without effort: we don't spend time thinking about what our hands are doing and how the sensory modalities help us in performing those actions. Many years are required to learn how to use our hands and to integrate them into our cognitive system [2]. The full achievement of skillful manipulations is typically referred to as "dexterity" [3].

The human grasping and manipulation behaviour has been widely studied and modelled, with the aim of either to design of healthy and safer products or to replicate the humans skill in a robot system [4].

The ways an object can be grasped are countless. At the higher level, the grasp can be described by the Grasp Type (GT, i.e., the pose of the fingers of the hand), the Grasp Location (GL, i.e., the location of the object target of the grasp), and the Grasp Dimension (GD, i.e., axis of opposition of the fingers respect to the object) [5]-[9]. The choice of the combination of GT, GL and GD (namely the grasp choice) in humans is influenced by five major factors: object constraints (e.g., shape, size, and function), task constraints (e.g., force and mobility), gripper constraints (e.g., the human hand or gripper kinematics and the hand or gripper size relative to the object to be grasped), habits of the grasper (e.g., experience and social convention), and chance (e.g., the initial position

of the object and environmental constraints) [9]. The grasp choice strongly depends by the situation and the weight of each factor changes case by case. In particular, since grasping is a purposive action [10], both the object and task constraints play an important role in the definition of the grasp choice. In robotics, purposive grasping [11] [12], has been studied considerably less than object grasping. However, in contrast with pick and place tasks that have no hard constraints, goal-oriented tasks require that the robot grasps the object with a precise orientation and leaves specific areas unobstructed so that the object can be used correctly. This aspect is even more important during collaborative actions such as object handover [9]. To efficiently hand over an object to the partner, humans account for both object affordances [13] and the partner's subsequent task to choose appropriately the GT and GL that allow the receiver to directly use the object [9]. Object deformability introduce hard constraints to the grasping. The influence of these constraints affects not only the GT and GL but also the wrist and body configurations to control and compensate deformations. How to synthesize all humans reasoning principles in a robotic system still remains an open challenge. The APRIL project (<https://aprilproject.eu/>) meets this challenge with the development of a new Grasp Library for flexible material and collaborative work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The Grasp Pipeline within APRIL

The APRIL project aims at developing autonomous and dexterous robots to innovate the manufacturing of flexible and deformable materials. The APRIL control architecture is characterized by three different layers: upper, middle, and lower layers. The grasp pipeline has a central role and it involves different components: the Knowledge Reasoning Engine Module (KREM), the High-level Control Engine Module (HICEM), the Low-level Control Engine Module (LOCEM), and the Learning Engine Module (LEM). The Grasp Library is part of the KREM and it returns to the HICEM the ranked list of semantic combinations of GT, GL, and GD. The Grasp Selector within the HICEM receives the best grasp choice (semantically described) and returns as output its numerical description as a list of possible hand and fingers trajectories contained in the Grasp Dictionary database. The trajectories recalled from the dictionary are validated by the LOCEM, which feedbacks the ones that can be executed by the robot (e.g., avoiding collisions or that are within the reachable workspace of the robot). Then, based on the plan, the HICEM asks to the LOCEM for the execution of the grasp. After that, the Grasp Refinement within the

LEM refines the grasp trajectory according to the output returned by the Grasp Stability component.

B. Grasp Library approach and architecture

The Grasp Library is a grasp planner that uses a symbolic representation of scenario to deduce the most suitable grasping option. The rationale driving the Grasp Library algorithm is drawn from human insights, motivated by four primary factors. Firstly most of the products, industrial equipment and the environments are designed for people and thus for being manipulated with humans hands. Secondly (and this also related to the first consideration) in the APRIL project robots exploit anthropomorphic robotic hands whose shape enables them to carry out movements that can be very similar to the human ones. Thirdly the extensive experience gained by humans over the years made their grasp choice extremely effective and adaptable. Lastly, by instilling human-like behaviour in a robot, the efficacy of Human-Robot collaboration enhances, consequently boosting the acceptance of robot by humans.

The Grasp Library is composed of the Knowledge and the Reasoning blocks (Fig. 1). The Knowledge block provides to the Reasoning block the symbolic description in terms of:

- Object constraints: weight, deformability, Center of Mass (CoM), size.
- Task constraints: aim (e.g., direct use and handover), constraints (e.g., specific area of the object that has to interact first with the environment).
- Gripper constraints: kinematics.
- Environment constraints: object occlusions due to the interaction with the environment.

Based on this information, the Reasoning block returns the ranked list of combinations of GT, GL, and GD as semantical output. The GT describes the posture of fingers contacting the object. The GL describes the area of the object contacted by the hand (Fig. 2 (a)). The areas that can be grasped (possible graspable areas) are defined according to three different parameters: (1) functionalities of the object; (2) shape of the object; (3) size of the gripper. The GD is the dimension of the object that lies between the fingers during the grasp (Fig. 2 (b)). Referring to [7], the three major dimensions are defined as a, b, and c, corresponding to the three axes of the bounding box enclosing the GL. The dimension a is along the longest dimension of the box shape; instead, c corresponds to the shortest dimension of the box shape. In the case of concave GLs, we added the dimension d to describe the wall thickness of the concavity.

Fig. 1 The Grasp Library architecture.

Fig. 2 (a) Segmentation of an insole into two GLs. (b) GDs representation for the tip GL.

C. Reasoning algorithm

The algorithm of the Grasp Library is based on rules defined according to the findings of behavioural studies on grasping and manipulation in humans. Each rule takes into account part of the knowledge related to object, task, gripper, and environmental constraints (Section II, Paragraph B). The algorithm performs a sequence of three actions: clean, rank, pair (Fig. 1). In the following, we report a description of the three actions:

1) Clean

The Grasp Library algorithm cleans the list of possible combinations of GL and GD from the ones that cannot be achieved by the robot due to physical constraints. This means removing the followings:

- The combinations of GL and GD which involve GDs non-physically graspable due to the proximity with the other GLs;
- The combination of GL and GD which are non-physically graspable due to the interaction with the environment (i.e., object occlusions).

2) Rank

The Grasp Library algorithm performs two rankings (see Section II, Paragraph D): the ranking of the possible combinations of GL and GD and the ranking of the possible GTs. In the text below, we define “grasp candidate” a possible combination of GL and GD or a possible GT used to grasp the object. The two rankings are obtained in the same way. First, each ranking rule assigns an integer penalty value to each grasp candidate: the lowest value corresponds to the preferred choice, while the highest value corresponds to the worst one. Secondly, for each grasp candidate, the algorithm performs the sum of the penalty values in order to produce the ranked list of combinations of GL and GD and the ranked list of GTs.

3) Pair

The final ranked list of GT, GL, GD is obtained by pairing the ranked list of combinations of GL and GD and the ranked list of GT. More specifically, the pairing considers the combinations of GL-GD and GTs according to the following criteria:

- The size of the GD is greater than the distance between fingers when the gripper is in the GT pre-shape;
- The sizes of the GDs perpendicular to the GD are lower than the width of the gripper.

Then, the elements of the lists are matched considering the following principle:

- The higher priority is given to the list of GTs in the case of heavy objects. So, the first element of the list of GTs is paired with all the combinations of GL and GD before passing to the second element of the list of GT.
- On the other hand, in the case of light objects, the higher priority is given to the combinations of GL-GD. In this case, the first combination of GL-GD is paired with all the GTs before passing to the second combination of GL-GD.

D. Ranking algorithm

1) Ranking Grasp Location and Grasp Dimension pairs

Humans have different goals if they have to directly use the object rather than handing over the object [9]. In the first case, humans aim to accomplish the task; in the latter case, they desire to make comfortable the receiver during the handover by considering the subsequent task he has to perform. Since the aim is different, the ranking algorithm (Fig. 3) acts differently in the two cases.

a) Direct use

In the case of direct use, the algorithm considers the following three rules.

- Rule 1 – Exploiting the object in the task

The task is defined as constrained if there is a specific area of the object that has to interact first with the environment. We call this area Use Location (UL). The task cannot be completed if the UL is obstructed [9]. According to this consideration, the ranking algorithm assigns the maximum penalty to the UL and zero penalties to the other object areas. The maximum penalty ensures that the UL is grasped as last. If the task is unconstrained, the ranking algorithm doesn't act.

- Rule 2 – Influence of the object deformability and task accuracy

If the task is constrained, we proved that the selected GL is closer to the UL the higher the deformability of the object; furthermore, the GL-UL distance decreases as the degree of deformability of the object or the precision required by the task increases. According to this consideration, in the case of constrained tasks using deformable objects, the ranking algorithm assigns increasing penalties moving away from the UL. Since the task is constrained, the UL is excluded from the ranking. In all the other cases, this ranking rule doesn't act.

Algorithm 1 Ranking algorithm for Grasp Location - Dimension

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1:  $ul \leftarrow gl \in \{gl, gd\}^{unsorted}$   $\triangleright$  use location
2:  $com \leftarrow gl \in \{gl, gd\}^{unsorted}$   $\triangleright$  center of mass location
3: procedure RANKINGGL-D( $\{gl, gd\}^{unsorted}$ )
4:   if  $handover$  then
5:     if constrained task then
6:       Assign the maximum penalty to  $ul$ ;
7:       if deformable object then
8:         Assign increasing penalty moving away from the  $ul$ ;
9:       if heavy object then
10:        Assign increasing penalty moving away from the  $com$ ;
11:   else if handover then
12:     if constrained task then
13:       Assign the minimum penalty to the  $ul$ ;
14:     else
15:       Assign the minimum penalty to the extremities;
16:     if heavy object then
17:       Assign increasing getting close to the  $com$ ;
18:   return  $\{gl, gd\}^{sorted}$ 

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Fig. 3 Ranking algorithm for the pairs of Grasp Location and Dimension.

- Rule 3 – Influence of the object weight

As proved in several studies [14] [15], the GL is closer to the object's CoM when grasping heavy compared to light objects. According to this consideration, in the case of heavy objects, the ranking algorithm assigns increasing penalties moving away from the CoM of the object. The CoM is included in the ranking. In the case of light objects, the ranking algorithm doesn't act.

b) Handover

In the case of handover, the algorithm considers the following two rules:

- Rule 1 – Considering the comfort and the ergonomics of the human receiver

When humans plan the grasp action for handling over an object, they take into account the subsequent task the receiver has to perform [9]. If the subsequent task is constrained, the passer plans the grasp with the aim of making comfortable the execution of the subsequent task; if the subsequent task is unconstrained, the passer plans the grasp with the aim of making the object handover comfortable by leaving unobstructed as many object areas as possible. According to these considerations, in the case of a constrained task, the ranking algorithm assigns the minimum penalty to the UL. This guarantees the receiver doesn't grasp the UL (because grasped by the passer) so that it can be exploited by the receiver for the execution of the subsequent task. In the case of unconstrained tasks, the ranking algorithm assigns the minimum penalties to the extreme areas of the object. This guarantees that most of the areas of the object are unobstructed and the handover results fluent.

- Rule 2 – Influence of the object weight

Humans tend to grasp heavy objects near their CoM (Section II, Paragraph D, item a) (Rule 3)). According to this consideration, in the case of heavy objects, the ranking algorithm assigns increasing penalties moving away from the object CoM (CoM included). If the object is light, this ranking rule doesn't act.

2) Ranking the Grasp Types

The rule at the basis of the ranking of the possible GTs is presented below (Fig. 4).

- Rule 1 – Influence of the object weight

As the object increases in size and mass, the number of fingers and the contact areas involved in the grasp increases [6]. For this reason, specific GTs are preferred based on the object's weight. According to [7], in the case of heavy objects, the algorithm assigns the minimum penalty to power GTs. In the case of light objects, the ranking algorithm assigns the minimum penalty to precision or intermediate GTs.

Algorithm 2 Ranking algorithm for Grasp Types

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1: procedure RANKINGGT( $\{gt\}^{unsorted}$ )
2:   if heavy object then
3:     for each  $gt \in \{gt\}^{unsorted}$  do
4:       if  $gt$  is power then
5:         Assign the minimum penalty to  $gt$ ;
6:   else if light object then
7:     for each  $gt \in \{gt\}^{unsorted}$  do
8:       if  $gt$  is precision or intermediate then
9:         Assign the minimum penalty to  $gt$ ;
10:  return  $\{gt\}^{sorted}$ 

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Fig. 4 Ranking algorithm for the Grasp Types.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We developed a new robot grasp planner dubbed as Grasp Library. It is able to provide a ranked list of semantical grasp candidate knowing the semantical description of the current situation. The main strength of the Grasp Library lays in its generality and modularity. The reasoning algorithm applies rules taking into account object, task, gripper, and environmental constraints. Once that information is provided as input, the Grasp Library is able to produce a ranking of grasp candidates. This makes the Grasp Library general with respect to new objects, tasks and robots. The modularity is given by the structure which includes several rules and is designed to accommodate new ones. Whenever new behavioural studies on human grasping are conducted, the Grasp Library structure is prepared to introduce the new findings between the rules guiding the grasp choice. In addition, unlike learning-based approaches, the Grasp Library doesn't require training (that is really time-consuming) and the output is eligible by definition. There are many possibilities for improving the current framework. With the aim of introducing new principles into the Grasp Library framework, new studies on human grasping behaviour can be conducted by considering the interactions of factors (e.g. weight and deformability) in the choice of the grasp. In addition, bimanual grasping can be also considered as a future development.

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